

INVESTIGATION ON THE ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE OF THE STAFF WORKING ON PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SPORTS INSTITUTIONS

Abdurrahman Kepođlu¹ⁱ

Ümmü Gülsüm Çakmak²

¹Assoc. Prof. Dr., Muđla Sıtkı Koçman University,
Faculty of Sports Science, Turkey

²Muđla Sıtkı Koçman University,
Faculty of Sports Science, Turkey

Abstract:

The purpose of our research is to examine the effect of job satisfaction on organizational culture of staff working in public and private sports organizations. The universe of our research is made up of public and private sports organization staff. Our sample is composed of staff working in public and private sports organizations in Aegean Region. As a data collection tool in the research, Personal information form, Minnesota job satisfaction scale, and Denison organizational culture scale have been used. The first validity and reliability studies of the Minnesota job satisfaction scale were conducted by Baycan (1985) with an alpha coefficient of 0.77. Reliability value was found to be 0.87 by Özdayı (1990). The confidence scale (Cronbach Alpha) adapted by Denison organizational culture scale to Gökşen (2001) and later (2002) was found 0.96. Through descriptive statistics, frequency, arithmetic mean, standard deviation values are determined. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test was used at 0,05 significance level to determine whether the data showed normal distribution. As a result of the test statistic, it was determined that the data were not the normal distribution. For this reason, non-parametric test statistic was used. The Mann Whitney-U test was used at a significance level of 0,05 in comparing the arithmetic mean of the binary groups. The Kruskal Wallis Test was used at a significance level of 0,05 in comparing the arithmetic mean of multiple groups. The existence of the correlation between job satisfaction and organizational culture was used at Pearson Correlation Analysis at the significance level

ⁱ Correspondence: email abdurrahmankepoglu@mu.edu.tr

of 0,05 and 0,01. Regression Analysis was used at a significance level of 0.05 for the determination of the degree of job satisfaction affecting the organizational culture. As a result of the research; It was found that there was a strong positive correlation between job satisfaction level and organizational culture level ($p < 0.01$) and half of the effect of job satisfaction ($R^2 = , 552$) on the formation of organizational cultures of public and private sports institutions. This result shows that the organization's staff will make a positive contribution to the formation of the organization's culture by taking measures to increase job satisfaction.

Keywords: organizational culture, staff working, public and private sports institutions

1. Introduction

Organization culture aims to gain the values of the staff employed in different departments within the organization, to respect the values of other staff, their beliefs and values, to establish a common aim within the organization and to act together for that purpose. In organizations that have formed an organization of cultures, works process faster and more efficiently. The staff who adopts the cultures of organisation works in a more efficient, coordinated and systematic manner in the work. Job satisfaction refers to the emotions that the staff feels towards their work and the performance they show towards their work. Job dissatisfaction refers to the reluctance of the staff to work and the discomfort to work and the institution. We can talk about two sub-dimensions in job satisfaction. First, the internal satisfaction which consists of Success, recognition, appreciation. The second is external satisfaction which consists of Salary, institutional policy, colleagues, and institutional management. If internal satisfaction and external satisfaction are ensured, the staff is satisfied with their work. Job satisfaction and organizational culture concepts are related to each other. The higher the job satisfaction, the more positive the organization will influence the organisation. Providing a good working environment for the staff and respecting the staff's feelings and thoughts will increase satisfaction in the staff as well as increasing organizational commitment and organizational alignment.

Throughout the working life, the staff has been gaining a lot of experience in the work they do and the institution they work in. During the working life of the staff, they have seen, lived, earned, lost, become happy and sad. As a result of all these knowledge and emotions, the staff has an attitude towards the work they are doing or the company they are working with. Job satisfaction is a result of these attitudes and indicates that

the staff is in good physical and mental terms (Aşık, 2010; Cornelieben, 2009; Sympane, Rieger and Roodt, 2002).

Initial studies on job satisfaction began with the Hawthorne studies of Elton Mayo in the 1930s. However, these studies are not a theoretical quality (Türk, 2007). It is the result of research on the motivation of the foundation of work related to job satisfaction. The first studies on human motivation are based on the scientific work developed by Frederick Winslow Taylor and Henry Fayol (Özaydın and Özdemir, 2014).

Job satisfaction, which focuses on employee attitudes, has attracted considerable attention since its involvement in organizational behavior studies in the 1930s. Initially studied by Hoppock in 1935, the correlation between job satisfaction & productivity and job performance was examined. Luthans pointed out three important dimensions of job satisfaction. These are (Luthans, 1995; Akt: Kaya, 2013):

- Job satisfaction is the emotional response the staff shows. So it cannot be observed but can be expressed.
- Earnings and expectations in job satisfaction are very important. The higher the expectations of the staff and the higher the gain, the happier it will be
- Factors such as working environment, manager and staff attitude, wage status, promotion and rewards directly affect job satisfaction.

The concept of job satisfaction holds an important place among the subjects of organizational behavior and human resources disciplines in order to respond to the expectations of the staff from the organization, to make them work more efficiently to contribute to the formation of a healthy and happy workforce and to protect the social balances (Pekdemir, Özçelik, Karabulut and Arslantaş, 2006).

In 1994, Barnard organization asserted that; two or more consciously coordinated activities, or a system of powers, and that an organization has come to fruition when it comes to communicating with each other, volunteering to support to reach a common goal.

Organization culture was described as below by Mwaura, Grace, Roberts, Silver, Uyar, Peter's, Waterman, Sabuncuoğlu and Tüz as described below. According to these definitions;

Organizational culture is a set of assumptions that have been proven to be valid by a certain group in a way that can be proved to be valid in the context of its integration in the group and its integration within the group, and thus taught as the right way to perceive, think and feel the new members' programs (Aydınlı, 2008).

Mwaura, Sutton, and Diane (1998) defined the organization's culture as the shared beliefs, attitudes, and values shared within the organization.

According to Gümüş (2011), organizational culture is a social knowledge that applies to a group at a specific time, loading martial schemes by arranging behaviors. Organizational culture refers to values, beliefs and assumptions as a subculture of collecting. They act as an identity for members, making them easier to perceive each other (Uyar, 2013).

One of the most used definitions is Peters and Waterman's (1982) definition of "The whole shared values" (Peters and Waterman, 1982). All material and moral values shared in an organization constitute the organization's culture. Since these values differ in all organizations, each organization has its own culture structure.

Management must find their own organizational culture model and work on it. In our study, we examined the influence of the Denison Organizational Culture model on institutions. This model divided the culture into four sub-dimensions. The first is the culture of participation; Organizational integrity and the ability of staff, teamwork and responsibility. The second is the culture of consistency; the internal integration of the organization to the foreground, to ensure the formation of common ideas and coordination. Third harmony culture; the organization attaches importance to the external environment, is open to change and is customer-focused. The fourth is mission culture, attaching importance to the relationship between the organization and the external environment. Determining the paths must be followed in order to reach the future where you want to be, and the staff who knows and understands them will cultivate the culture of the organization and consciously cultivate the organization culture in the institution.

In organizations that have formed an organization of cultures, things move faster and more efficiently. The organization works in a more efficient, coordinated and systematic manner in the work of the staff who adopt the cultures.

Job satisfaction and organizational culture concepts are related to each other. The higher the job satisfaction, the more positive the organization will influence the organization. Providing a good working environment for the staff and respecting the staff's feelings and thoughts will increase satisfaction in the staff as well as increasing organizational commitment and organizational alignment.

2. Method

Our research has been prepared in accordance with a descriptive research model. In this research model, the case examined by the researcher is not changed. An attempt is made to identify the present situation. The universe of the research consists of 702 public and 499 private sports organizations staff working in the Aegean region. The

sample of the research is as follows: 313 public staff and 379 private sports organizations were employed in Mugla, Aydın and İzmir provinces randomly selected from the Aegean region.

The Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale, the most widely used measure of job satisfaction, was used a 20-item short form to measure job satisfaction in this study. The scale was first used by Baycan in his research and the scale was collected in two dimensions as internal and external satisfaction. The scale consisted of 20 questions where 12 questions were as identified internal factors, while the remaining 8 was identified as the internal factors. This Likert scale is rated as 5 and the answers sample groups were as followed. "*I am not satisfied at all, I am not satisfied, I am undecided, satisfied and very satisfied*". The validity value of our scale in our study was 82.

The Denison Culture Scale, which was developed by Denison and Mishra in 1995, consists of 60 phrases which include 4 basic dimensions and 12 conceptual sub-dimensions. The validity and reliability tests of the scale were made by Denison, Mishra and Jae Cho and are statistically significant. The Denison Organizational Culture Scale was adapted to Turkish by Gökşen (2001) and the reliability coefficient (Cronbach Alpha) was found to be 0.96. Yahyagil (2004) created the form of 36 expressions in which each of the 12 sub-dimensions of the scale is represented by three expressions, and it is valid and reliable The Denison measuring instrument was developed to measure the cultural profile of organizations. This model is based on four basic characteristics on which effective organizations are based. These features are Participation, consistency, compliance and mission. Each conceptual dimension consists of 3 sub-conceptual dimensions. The validity value of our scale was found to be 76.

In the analysis of the data, SPSS 18.0 program was used. Through descriptive statistics, frequency, arithmetic mean, standard deviation values were determined. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test was used at 0,05 significance level to determine whether the data showed normal distribution. As a result of the test statistic, it was determined that the data were not distributed normally. For this reason, nonparametric test statistic was used. The Mann Whitney-U test was used at a significance level of 0,05 in comparing the arithmetic mean of the binary groups. The Kruskal Wallis Test was used at a significance level of 0 to 5 in the comparison of the arithmetic mean of multiple groups. The existence of the correlation between job satisfaction and organizational culture was used at Pearson Correlation Analysis at 0,05 and 0,01 significance level. Regression Analysis was used at a significance level of 0.05 for the determination of the degree of job satisfaction affecting the organizational culture.

3. Findings

Demographic characteristics of staff employed in public and private sports organizations are as follows. 80.4% of the sample staff participated in our research and 19.6% work in the private sports organization. 36% of the staff are women and 64% are men. 57.7% of the staff are married and 42.3% are single. 9.4% of the sample staff in our study were at the age of 18-24, 42.9% were at the age of 25-34, 29.9% were at the age of 35-44, 13.9% were at the age of 45-54 and 3.9% were at the age of 55 and over. 50.8% of the sample staff had sports training and 49.2% did not have any sports training. 0.3% of the staff participating in the study were provincial directors, 2.4% were district managers, 0.9% were youth center managers, 2.1% were branch managers, 3.3% were chiefs, 17.2% were sports education specialists, 25.4% were coach, 6.9% were assisted staff, 15.4% were civil servants, 7.3% were leaders and 18.7% were in other units. 45.9% of the sample staff participating in the study has 1300-2500 TL/month salary, 41.7% of them have 2501 - 3500 TL/month salary and 12.4% of them have 3500 TL/month or over income. 18.1% of the staff are working in the institution for 0-1 years, 21.1% are working for 6-15 years and 22.7% are working for 16 or over years.

Table 1: Job Satisfaction Levels of Public and Private Sports Organization Employees

Institution		N	$\bar{X}$	σ
Public Organisation	Internal satisfaction level	266	70,3947	17,31218
	Internal Dimension Satisfaction Level	266	43,1992	10,90654
	External Dimension Satisfaction Level	266	27,1955	6,93143
	N	266		
Private Organisation	Internal satisfaction level	65	83,0923	9,90064
	Internal Dimension Satisfaction Level	65	50,9231	5,88512
	External Dimension Satisfaction Level	65	32,1692	4,84951
	N	65		

It can be said that the level of job satisfaction of private sports organizations is higher than the level of job satisfaction of public sports organizations. It can be said that the internal dimension satisfaction level and the external dimension satisfaction level are high in public institutions and that the internal dimension satisfaction level is high and the external dimension satisfaction level is high in private institutions.

Table 2: Mann-Whitney U Test Regarding Job Satisfaction Level, Internal Dimension Satisfaction Level, and External Dimension Satisfaction Level According to the institutions

	Institution	N	$\bar{X}$ Rank
Internal satisfaction level	Public Organisation	266	150,86
	Private Organisation	65	227,94
	Total	331	
Internal Dimension Satisfaction Level	Public Organisation	266	151,56
	Private Organisation	65	225,09
	Total	331	
External Dimension Satisfaction Level	Public Organisation	266	151,70
	Private Organisation	65	224,54
	Total	331	

	Internal satisfaction level	Internal Dimension Satisfaction Level	External Dimension Satisfaction Level
Mann-Whitney U	4619,000	4,804E3	4840,000
Wilcoxon W	40130,000	4,032E4	4,035E4
Z	-5,823	-5,558	-5,509
P	,000	,000	,000
Variable: Institutions			

There is a significant difference between the type of institution in which employees work and job satisfaction levels ($p < 0.05$).

Significant differences were found between the type of institution where the staff worked and the internal dimension satisfaction levels ($p < 0,05$).

Significant differences were found between the type of institution the staff worked and the external dimension satisfaction levels ($p < 0.05$).

Table 3: Organizational Culture of Public and Private Sports Organization Employees by Institution; Participation, Consistency, Compliance and Mission Culture Levels

Kurum		N	$\bar{X}$	σ
Public Organisation	Organizational Culture Level	263	1,1304E2	26,60630
	Participation Culture	264	28,1364	7,65489
	Coherency Culture	265	28,1585	7,01496
	Harmony Culture	266	28,3835	6,81809
	Mission Culture	266	28,3684	7,19011
	N	263		
Private Organisation	Organizational Culture Level	64	1,4098E2	19,23744
	Participation Culture	65	36,1077	6,05218
	Coherency Culture	64	34,2188	5,75000

Abdurrahman Kepoğlu, Ümmü Gülsüm Çakmak
 INVESTIGATION ON THE ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE OF THE STAFF WORKING ON
 PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SPORTS INSTITUTIONS

	Harmony Culture	65	35,8769	4,88463
	Mission Culture	65	34,7846	5,92002
	N	64		

When we look at public and private organizations; It can be said that the levels of participation culture, coherence culture, adaptation culture and mission culture are higher, but it can be said that the level of organizational culture of private sports organizations is higher than that of the organizational culture of public organizations.

Table 53: Correlation Analysis of Connection Between Job Satisfaction and Organizational Culture

Descriptive Statistics			
	$\bar{X}$	σ	N
Job Satisfaction Level	72,8882	16,88812	331
Organizational Culture Level	118,51	27,63554	327

Correlation			
		Job Satisfaction Level	Organizational Culture Level
Job Satisfaction Level	Pearson Correlation	1	,744**
	P		,000
	N	331	327
Organizational Culture Level	Pearson Correlation	,744**	1
	P	,000	
	N	327	327
**. P < 0.01			

There is a strong positive correlation between job satisfaction level and organizational culture level ($p < 0.01$).

Table 54: Regression Analysis on the Effect of Job Satisfaction on Organizational Culture

Model Abstract				
Model	R	R ²	Residual R ²	Estimated Standard Error
1	,744 ^a	,554	,552	18,48736
a. Job Satisfaction Level				

ANOVA ^b						
Model		Total Square	sd	Square of the mean	F	p
1	Regression	137894,459	1	137894,459	403,457	,000 ^a
	Residual value	111079,253	325	341,782		
	Total	248973,713	326			
a. Independent variable: Job Satisfaction Level						
b. Dependent variable: Organizational Culture Level						

C ^a						
Model		B	Standard error	Beta	t	p
	Job Satisfaction Level	1,211	,060	,744	20,086	,000
a. Dependent variable: Organizational Culture Level						

The effect of job satisfaction (R² = ,552) on the formation of organizational cultures of public and private sports organizations is half. This result shows that the measures to increase the job satisfaction of the staff of the institutions will contribute positively to the formation of organizational culture.

4. Results and Discussions

When the job satisfaction and sub-dimensions of staff working in public and private sports organizations are examined, it is seen that the staff working in private sports organizations have higher levels of internal and external satisfaction, which are both job

satisfactions and sub-dimensions of job satisfaction. However, the satisfaction level of the staff working in both public and private sports organizations is high.

When the levels of organizational culture and sub-dimensions of the staff working in public and private sports organizations are observed in the culture of participation, culture of coherence, culture of adaptation and mission culture, It is observed that the staff who work in private sport organizations have higher levels of participation culture, harmony culture and mission culture from both organizational cultures and organizational culture sub-dimensions. However, the level of organizational culture of the staff working in both public and private sports organizations is high.

There was a strong positive relationship between job satisfaction level and organizational culture level in our study. Similar results for our findings; (Özkan, 2016) a study of organizational communication, organizational culture and job satisfaction variables of subcontracted staff and staff (Guest, 2006). And in the study of Keskin (2014), a meaningful difference was found between job satisfaction and organizational culture. An increase in the level of organizational culture or an increase in job satisfaction will affect each other positively. As the level of job satisfaction is high, the organization should be viewed as a whole as it affects the culture positively and the performance of job satisfaction and organizational culture of the staff should be supported by in-service training, communication seminars and training.

References

1. Aşık, N. A. (2010). Çalışanların İş Doyumunu Etkileyen Bireysel ve Örgütsel Faktörler ile Sonuçlarına İlişkin Kavramsal Bir Değerlendirme. *Türk İdare Dergisi* 467: 31-51.
2. Aydınlı, M. T. (2008). *Örgüt Kültürünün Oluşturulmasında Öğretmen Davranışlarının Etkisi*. (Yayımlanmamış yüksek lisans tezi). Yeditepe Üniversitesi/Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, İstanbul.
3. Barnand, C. (1994). The Functions of Executive. *Cambridge: Harvard University Press* 122-125.
4. CorneliBen T. (2009). The Interaction of Job Satisfaction, Job Search, and Job Changes. An Empirical Investigation with German Panel Data. *J. Happiness Study*, 10: 367-384.

5. Demir, N. (2005). *Örgüt Kültürü- İş Tatmini İlişkisi: Plastik Sektöründe Bir Araştırma*. (Yayımlanmamış yüksek lisans tezi). İstanbul Üniversitesi / Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, İstanbul.
6. Gümüş, E.A. (2011). *İlköğretim Okullarında Çalışan Öğretmenlerin Yönetime Katılma Düzeyleri ile Örgüt Kültürü İlişkisinin İncelenmesi*. (Yayımlanmamış yüksek lisans tezi). Yeditepe Üniversitesi/Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, İstanbul.
7. Kaya, N. (2013). *İş Tatmini ve Örgütsel Bağlılık Arasındaki İlişki: Bir Uygulama*. (Yüksek lisans tezi). Marmara Üniversitesi/Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, İstanbul.
8. Keskin, B. (2014). *Kilmann ve Quinn-Cameron Modeline Göre Örgüt Kültürü İle İş Tatmini İlişkisi Üzerine Bir Araştırma*. (Yüksek lisans tezi). Marmara Üniversitesi/Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü İşletme Anabilim Dalı Yönetim ve Organizasyon Bilim Dalı, İstanbul.
9. Konuk M. (2006). *İşletmelerde Örgüt Kültürünün İş Tatmini Üzerindeki Etkisi ve Önemi Konya Şeker Fabrikasında Bir Uygulama*. (Yüksek lisans tezi). Selçuk Üniversitesi/Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü İşletme Anabilim Dalı Yönetim ve Organizasyon Bilim Dalı, Konya.
10. Oran, A. (2016). *Yükseköğretim Kurumlarında Örgüt Kültürünün, Çalışanların Örgütsel Bağlılık ve İş Tatmin Düzeyleri Açısından İncelenmesi*. (Yüksek lisans tezi). Aksaray Üniversitesi/Sosyal Bilimleri Enstitüsü İşletme Anabilim Dalı, Aksaray.
11. Özaydın, M. ve Özdemir, Ö. (2014). Çalışanların Bireysel Özelliklerinin İş Tatmini Üzerindeki Etkileri: Bir Kamu Bankası Örneđi. *İşletme Araştırmaları Dergisi*. 6 (1) s. 251-281.
12. Pekdemir, I., Özçelik, O., Karabulut, E. ve Arslantaş, C.C. (2006). Personel Güçlendirme, İş Tatmini ve Örgütsel Bağlılık Arasındaki İlişkileri Belirlemeye Yönelik Bir Çalışma. *Verimlilik Dergisi* Sayı.4.
13. Peters, T., Waterman, R.H. (1982). *Yönetme ve Yükseltme Sanatı - Mükemmeli Arayış*, S. Sargut (Çev.). İstanbul: Altın Kitapları.
14. Sempane, M.E., Rieger H.S., Roodt G. (2002). Job Satisfaction In Relation To Organisational Culture. *SA Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 28 (2); 23-30.
15. Türk, S. (2007). *Örgüt Kültürü ve İş Tatmini*. İstanbul: Gazi Kitabevi.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).